

PROSPECTS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF AN INNOVATIVE ECONOMY IN THE AGRARIAN SPHERE

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ABSTRACT

In this article, the policy of innovation in the agricultural sector is an important direction of the development of the economy of our country. Innovation is a process of economic development associated with the creation of an economic environment based on high technologies.

As a result of the introduction of scientific developments in the agricultural sector, the effective use of innovations, the development of non-traditional methods of innovation, and the creation of an innovation environment as the first factor in solving economic problems, an innovative money flow to the country occurs. Investing capital to increase the intellectual potential in agriculture is the main factor for the future development of the agrarian economy. It allows to develop innovative activity in this field, to expand the scope of scientific research, to increase the quality and scientific-practical significance of the introduction of innovative projects.

Innovative development in the fields is the development of society, development of society, innovative economic process.

Keywords: agrarian sphere, innovation, scientific product, financing, promotion, improvement, economy.

INTRODUCTION

The indicator of the share of the use of innovation as a source of increasing competitiveness of individual sectors of the economy is also different in conditions of the fact that the development of the world economy is not the same. The fact that the use of innovations by the country is not the same depends on the fact that the introduction of innovative production in the conditions of networks within the framework of a single economic system is not the same.

It is necessary to introduce innovations in the agrarian sphere of the country into practice and make effective use of them. It is necessary to attract a wide range of innovations to the economy, modernize production, achieve competitiveness and access to world markets, create opportunities for the production of import-substituting

and export-oriented products, employment of the population. Special attention is paid to attracting direct investments to the Real sector of our economy, a number of works are being carried out to stimulate them.

In addition to the achievements, there are a number of problems associated with the involvement of innovation in the economy of the agrarian sector: the fact that their participation in the promotion and implementation of investment projects in the activities of farmers and farmers in agriculture has not been effectively established; the lack of experience and knowledge of entrepreneurs working with innovation projects on; inadequate Organization of consulting, engineering, marketing and legal service centers in the Regions [1].

In the agrarian sphere, there is no system that provides for innovative development. This is due to some factors hindering the development of innovative activities in agriculture. Lack of material support for scientific and practical research hinders the economic development of innovation. Recently, very strong work is being carried out on the introduction of innovations based on new knowledge and scientific developments. This is a long - term task aimed at changing economic growth-innovation raw materials. Therefore, we believe that for the development of Technology, Science and innovation, it is necessary to invest directly in the entire agricultural sector, which should become the main factors of economic growth.

The technical and technological level of agriculture associated with the development of the innovation process is low, including the lack of scientific and technical progress and inadequate support of the innovation process. Since investments in agricultural innovation processes in the current conditions are of little importance to investors, the application of an active innovation policy requires the implementation of special measures that will allow to improve the investment system. At present, it is possible to carry out research work not only through the state network of financing and promotion of innovative activities, but also through indirect influence directly from the state budget.

Theoretical and practical problems associated with the need to improve the effectiveness of innovative process management, increase the innovative activity of economic entities in the field of Agriculture, the formation of innovation in their development and the update of methodological approaches in their implementation, determine in advance the choice of the relevance of the topic.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

The problem of innovation is the problem of our country, regions, individual sectors and enterprises, both on a global scale. It is diverse, complex, anti-dependent, associated with a mass of negative and positive factors, requires in-depth research and

vague answers. But it should be understood that the agrarian market economy of our country is not ideal, the situation factor is important. It plays a big role in the modern economy and informal rules, and this must also be taken into account.

At the same time, we note the low level of demand for new technologies by the economic operators of the agro-industrial complex. With full support of the results of this research work, it should be noted that on some priority sectors, the vast majority of agricultural products being sold also fall on personal assistant farms, this has led to a decline in the level of agricultural innovation in general. Here it is necessary to solve the problem of the need to develop extensive cooperation of individual auxiliary farms with farmers and peasant farms, agricultural enterprises of medium and large agricultural production and commodity farms. In this case, it is necessary to take into account all institutional omen that affect innovative activities.

Economists in the agrarian sector described the innovation as follows.

S. I. Nekrasov, H. A. Nekrasov and O. V. Busygin. Studied the evolution of organizational development models of enterprises and identified several types of such models: structural-situational, in national and selection [2].

A. I. Grischenkoy. The innovation process offers an understanding of the interconnected efforts of innovative beneficiaries to formulate scientific results, develop and commercialize innovations in the field of industrial development [3].

In our opinion, a person must have scientific developments and his own innovations in his activity, be able to apply it in any field, be able to realize it in the markets, have innovative features that will give results in economic and other types of directions.

Modernization of the economy of our country is impossible without investment, innovation and scientific staff. Our republic should take into account these recommendations in the development of the strategy for the development of Science and technology. The problems of transferring the agrarian sphere of the economy to the path of innovative development are due to the lack of a scientifically based program on the restoration and development of scientific and innovative activities, the lack of scientific developments on the promotion of the introduction of resource-saving technologies, their formation. With sufficient financial resources allocated for the implementation of this program, a fundamental state concept of the development and introduction of innovative techniques and technologies into the agrarian phere of the economy is necessary. The implementation of this program should include the implementation of Personnel Training and retraining measures. For the agricultural sector, it is necessary to create and more effective use of resource-saving technologies. The financial resources of the state used for the implementation of this program will be paid, since the introduction of these technologies will reduce the costs of agricultural

products and increase the profitability of agricultural producers, which is the amount that can pay all tax obligations to the budget.

The lack of demand is due to the fact that practical studies aimed at saving tangible resources for the production of agricultural products and the creation of environmentally friendly technologies are sufficiently developed-about half of agricultural organizations do not have the financial resources to order the development of innovative technologies for the production of food products. Scientific activity in the field of development of innovative technologies for the agrarian sphere of the economy is limited not only by adequate financing of these areas, but also by adequate development of scientific work in this area, the lack of scientific personnel specializing in these disciplines. The acquisition of innovative technologies of developed countries for the production of agricultural products is often carried out without analyzing its natural-climatic conditions, the level of qualification of the existing employees of these enterprises, without training the appropriate personnel, without the infrastructure of their service. Science and education are the first components of innovative development, the future of innovative development of the agrarian sphere of the economy depends on the public and private financial support of these areas.

N.V. Orlova rightly believes that innovation should be carried out as a process so that it is such for production and consumption [4].

To assess the economic and social results of innovative activities in the agrarian sphere, the following system of indicators can be used:

- approximation of the volume of investments in scientific research and agrarian production;
- share of innovative high-tech products in the total volume of the final output of the agrarian sphere;
- the impact of innovation on the effectiveness of the use of factors of production of enterprises of the agrarian sphere;
- the impact of innovation on the results of production and financial activities of enterprises in the agrarian sphere.

Methodology. Based on the research, conclusions are made, descriptions are given based on it. Development of innovative economy in agriculture, effectiveness of research and development activities, effective impact of funds directed to the economy of the republic as a result of analysis of their main directions. The goal of developing the innovative economy of the country is to establish a regional agricultural research center, to increase the income of farmers and peasant farms and to involve them in innovative projects, as well as to create a scientifically based and promising system of agricultural development. Scientific research and economic analysis methods were widely used in the research process.

DISCUSSION

The goal of introducing innovation into life is to achieve a single positive result. It can be understood from this that the sphere of innovation is closely related to the sphere of investment in itself. As the priority areas of innovation and investment activity in the conditions of development of the national economy, we can see the following: modernization of enterprises, further acceleration of technical and technological re-equipment, wide introduction of modern, flexible technologies; to implement specific measures to support the competitiveness of export-oriented enterprises in foreign markets and to create additional factors to promote exports; increase the competitiveness of real sector enterprises from the account of stimulating the reduction of production costs and product cost; implementation of measures to modernize the system of electro energetics, reduce energy consumption and introduce an effective system of energy saving; support local producers by encouraging demand in the domestic market.

Of course, the role of innovation in the modernization of the national economy and increasing its competitiveness can not be overemphasized. But for the organization and development of innovation activities in the country requires the existence and fulfillment of the following conditions: state innovation policy – development and determination by the bodies of the state power of the Republic of Uzbekistan of the goals of the country's innovative strategy and priority innovative programs and projects support; investment potential - the sum of the resources of the state, Network, enterprise and organization in different ways (including material, financial, intellectual, scientific-technical, economic, etc.); the sphere of innovation is the sphere of activity of producers and consumers of innovation products (work, service), which includes the creation and distribution of innovations; innovation infrastructure – various institutions that allow, influence the implementation of innovation activities; innovation program (enterprise, network, region, state, region, state) – innovative projects and activities that ensure the effective solution of tasks for the development and placement of new types of products, agreed on the resources, performers of innovation projects and their implementation deadlines.

The interaction of the economic situation of Uzbekistan with innovations can be seen in the following main aspects, namely, from the point of view of studying the impact of innovation activity on the national economy as a whole as a material basis of the state; to look at the impact of innovation on the activities of a particular enterprise as a separate market

Innovation in the conditions of modernization of the economy in Uzbekistan is necessary, first of all, for its sustainable growth. Investments in new technologies contribute to the production of goods consumed in competitive, high demand [5].

One of the main means of influencing the entrepreneurial activity of the country's economy and economic sectors is the policy of innovation, which is considered one of the pillars of the state economic policy. With the help of the state innovation policy, it is able to directly influence the increase in the rates of production, the acceleration of Science and technology development, the change in the structure of social production, the solution of social problems.

Innovative growth as a strategic direction for the development of the global economy in the coming decades will be provided mainly due to the convergence of technologies, during which there will be ample opportunities for the emergence of a huge range of technological directions at the junction of existing ones, which significantly expands the base for breakthrough innovations [6].

To assess the economic and social results of innovative activities in the agrarian sphere, the following system of indicators can be used: approximation of the volume of investments in scientific research and agrarian production; share of innovative high-tech products in the total volume of the final output of the agrarian sphere; the impact of innovation on the effectiveness of the use of factors of production of enterprises of the agrarian sphere; the impact of innovation on the results of production and financial activities of enterprises in the agrarian sphere.

RESULTS

Today, innovations in the agrarian sphere are manifested as a prerequisite for the economic growth and development of society. The use of innovation as a strategic factor of economic growth is very important, especially for the regions of our republic with high agricultural and agricultural potential. Along with the use of innovative technologies in agriculture, it is also associated with the possibility of creating and developing high-quality techniques and technologies.

The use of resources in the agrarian sphere is inextricably linked with increasing efficiency, carrying out innovative projects, attracting long-term investments to the economy, new forms of investment and economic development of the network. It is necessary to seek innovation and investment in the right direction and ways of effective use of investment. The country will be involved in financing investment projects for the modernization of strategic sectors of the economy. Positive changes should also be made in the context of attracting investments of developed countries to the Republic of Uzbekistan.

At present, the wider involvement of innovation and investment in the country's economy has become an important basis for ensuring their effective implementation at a new stage of economic reforms in the country. Therefore, one of the major problems is economic promotion of agricultural enterprises attracting foreign investment to the country and the creation important conditions.

The equilibrium development of the economy depends on the real growth of the gross domestic product, the positive dynamics of the main macroeconomic indicators, such as inflation, the exchange rate, the unemployment rate, and the balance of payments. Economic growth is primarily expressed in the quantitative growth in the volume of goods and services produced, as well as in qualitative changes.

Without increasing the volume of production of agricultural products in the country, without increasing the efficiency of the use of farmer and peasant land, without increasing the productivity of new energy-saving technologies and land, a tangible result can't be achieved.

Serious changes in the structure of investments in the economy and foreign investments aimed at the economy occupy a leading place in the agrarian sector. Attracting investments in the agrarian economy of the country is aimed not only at the implementation of promising projects in cooperation with foreign countries, but also at ensuring the high quality of the products produced on this basis, the introduction of new modern techniques and technologies.

Political factors: the liberalization of capital exports; the policy of indoctrination in developing countries; the conduct of new invasions of economic reforms, that is, state enterprises privatization, support of farmer and peasant farms; conduct policies to maintain employment levels.

Attracting investments and long-term investment loans, radical modernization of the production base of the economy, its technical and technological re-equipment is the most decisive task.

Political and economic stability in the country gives an opportunity to attract investments in the agrarian sector. The fact that the legal basis of the investment policy has also been restored in order to ensure the consistent development of the industry has ensured the introduction of a certain amount of investments in the sector in recent years.

The Republic of Uzbekistan has adopted state programs on the cultivation of agricultural products, these programs are provided for the implementation of works on the project by the Ministry of Agriculture to finance investment activities. Works on projects by the Ministry of agriculture are carried out mainly under the state guarantee. There must be a guarantee that the subjects financing the implementation of the project will return their investments with a certain degree of profit. The return on investment will be through the proceeds from the processing and sale of the product under

cultivation. In the innovation project, this factor should be expressed. Therefore, each subject participating in the innovation process must clearly demonstrate its material viability.

This is due to the mechanism of distribution of revenue from the sale of grown products. At the same time, their share in the production of innovative products should be proportionally distributed among its subjects.

The orientation of agriculture towards the path of innovative development can be determined by analyzing the ability, capacity and readiness of the enterprise, farmers and peasant farms to innovate [7].

The agrarian sphere proposes the following to address the problems of attracting investments to the economy: conducting in-depth marketing research on the investment project; stability of the cash flow of the investment project; positive impact on the reliability of the source of repayment of the loan received for financing the investment project; it is important that the investment plan be applied in order to avoid problematic tasks, the formation of a more favorable investment microclimate for the sustainable improvement of the agricultural sector, activation and implementation of investments in the network should come first.

According to the innovative model, the basis of economic strategy in developing countries is not only the development of high – tech production, but also the achievement of an innovative balance sheet-the optimization of the role and volume of the innovative component. This approach formulates a special attitude of business and society to the development of high-tech complex productions and the conduct of a wide range of research and experimental design work, which involves the development of the economy in an innovative way [8].

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, we emphasize a number of main works and measures aimed at the formation and further development of an innovative economy in the Republic of Uzbekistan:

- gradual application of the experience of developed countries to the branches of the economy of the Republic, proceeding from our national interests;
- attracting investors and foreign capital to domestic innovative projects of great importance;
- establish a knowledge base dedicated to technological innovations and in it access of all citizens through the internet portal;
- development of innovations, ensuring reliable protection of property in the transformation of achievements in this area into high added value.

The stability of the agrarian sphere of the economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan directly related to the possibility of implementing innovative development by the majority economic entities of Agriculture.

It established that the innovative agrarian economy is an economy based on the search, preparation and implementation of investments that increase the level of satisfaction of the needs of society in food resources. Innovative activity in agrarian sphere characterized as a complex process of introducing advanced technical, technological, organizational, economic and managerial solutions, creating new or more effective high-yielding varieties, breeding cattle, elite seeds, high-performance agricultural machines and aggregates, etc.

The modern conditions for the transfer of the country's economy to the path of innovative development impose new requirements for the organization of innovations and are characterized by the need to replace equipment, develop, introduce new technologies, introduce technological competition, fundamental and Applied Research.

REFERENCES:

1. Ushachev I.G., Sandu I.S., Nechaev V.I. i dr. (2017) Prioritetnie napravleniya innovatsionnogo razvitiya APK sovremennoy Rossii. Metodologicheskie podxodi: monografiya. 140.
2. Nekrasov S.I. (2009) Faktori organizatsionnogo razvitiya predpriyatiy / C.I. Nekrasov, N.A. Nekrasova, O.V. Busigin. Izd-vo "Akademiya estestvoznaniya", 156.
3. Gritshenkov A.I. (2011) Razrabotka metodiki upravleniya innovatsionnimi proessami v ramkax setevoy ekonomiki / A.I. Gritshenkov, N.V. Glushak. - Bryansk: Izd-vo OOO "Ladimir", 342.
4. Orlova N.V. (2010) Instrumenti obespecheniya innovatsionnogo razvitiya ekonomiki Rossii / N.V. Orlova. - Saratov: OOO Izdatelskiy tsentr "Nauka", 148.
5. A.Babadjanov, F.Shafkarov. (2022) Improving the Mechanism of Public-Private Partnership in the Financing and Implementation of Projects in the Networks of the Infrastructure of the Agro-Industrial Complex. International Journal of Discoveries and Innovations in Applied Sciences (IJDIAS) ISSN 2792-3983. 2(10), 33-49.
6. Baydakov A.N., Chernikova L.I., Nazarenko A.V. et al. (2017) Scenario Forecasting of the Reproduction Process in the Agriculture in View of Inflation. Journal of Environmental Management and Tourism, 8(3), 620–628.
7. A.Babadjanov (2022) scientific basis of innovative development of production in the agrarian sector. Economics and education, (1), 312-317.
8. Krasnova N.A. (2012) Rol gosudarstvennoy podderjki v formirovanii innovatsionnoy strategii razvitiya APK. - Regionalnaya ekonomika i upravlenie: elektronniy nauchniy jurnal, (31), 10-18.